

STUDY OF THE PROPERTIES OF HIGH EFFICIENT SOLAR ELEMENTS BASED ON SEMICONDUCTORS

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Annotation: *This article discusses how to increase the efficiency of solar photogenerators and the factors associated with them.*

Keywords: *photocell, semiconductors, conventional energy, solar cell, effective layer, optical efficiency, photogenerator.*

Semiconductor photocells (solar batteries) are simple sources of electricity that can convert light energy from the sun directly into electricity. Although photogenerators are still used successfully in many industries, the energy cost of generating them is much higher than that of conventional electricity. This will require more research to improve the efficiency of photogenerators. Improving the efficiency of solar photovoltaic generators depends on many factors. It is not enough to choose a semiconductor material with good performance. The use of complex semiconductors in the manufacture of photocells has shown promising results. Such photocells are able to work even in the conditions of concentrated light. Any research aimed at improving the efficiency of solar photovoltaic cells is aimed at making full use of incoming solar energy, reducing the cost of the device, as well as increasing the unit capacity of the device. It is natural that any research in this area will help solve the problems associated with increasing the efficiency of solar photovoltaic generators.

In the future, it is possible to increase the FIC to 24% by creating photocells (cascade photocells) consisting of a layer of semiconductors with different forbidden areas. The capabilities of ultra-thin layer solar cells are much better [1].

Gallium arsenide is another semiconductor material suitable for solar photovoltaic devices. The FIC of solar cells based on this semiconductor is stable even at high temperatures and their specific power does not change up to 500K [2]. Due to the limited use of gallium arsenide, the availability of gallium reserves, its extraction and chemical treatment pose certain difficulties. Solar power plants must be made of non-defective materials, have a simple manufacturing process, and have similar properties when manufactured on a large scale. Today, solar photovoltaic devices typically use r-p transition photocells that are resistant to radiation flux. Solar photovoltaic devices often use silicon solar cells with r-p transitions. At present, completely improved solar cells are being produced. In the following years, silicon solar cells have been sufficiently improved and effective layered solar cells have been created that provide illumination, thermoregulation and radiation protection. Solar cells with a non-reflective surface, known as the "absolute black" solar cell, are becoming increasingly important. The optical characteristics of r-p-structures and photoelectric devices are strongly related primarily to the optical properties of the surface of the material used as the base [3]. Although there are many types of anti-reflective coatings on silicon surfaces, their systematic application in single- and multilayer systems, depending on the value and thickness of the physical refractive index, has not been studied by digital modeling. Research on texture and the application of additional anti-reflective coatings is also not systematized. In order to create a photoelectric device with high optical efficiency, the first step is to select a semiconductor material based on its light absorption characteristics; secondly, the thickness of the semiconductor material and thirdly the quality of its surface treatment; fourth, a scientific approach is required to factors such as surface defects and passivation of various conditions leading to recombination of photogenerated charge carriers [4]. That is, one of the most important tasks is to improve the optical efficiency of photovoltaic devices. These

devices are highly sensitive in the short-wavelength part of the solar spectrum and consist of a thin base and an ultra-thin layer of silicon. The FIC of such a device is in the order of specific power 0.9-1.3 W / g, in addition, they have a two-way sensitivity. An analysis of the experimental results shows that the FIC of the silicon solar cell is currently 16% [5].

In short, in the future it is possible to increase the FIC to 24% by creating photocells (cascade photocells) consisting of a layer of semiconductors with different forbidden areas. The capabilities of ultra-thin layered solar cells are much better.

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